

WIDENING THE PATH FOR DEMAND-SIDE FLEXIBILITY SERVICES IN EUROPEAN HOUSEHOLDS

Joint findings of the FLEXCoop
& HOLISDER projects in
standardization & Interoperability

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For more information: More information, including technical details, can be found in the projects' deliverables available on the two projects' websites.

FLEXCoop

WWW.FLEXCOOP.EU

[HTTPS://CORDIS.EUROPA.EU/PROJECT/ID/773909](https://CORDIS.EUROPA.EU/PROJECT/ID/773909)

HOLISDER

WWW.HOLISDER.EU

[HTTPS://CORDIS.EUROPA.EU/PROJECT/ID/768614](https://CORDIS.EUROPA.EU/PROJECT/ID/768614)

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INTRODUCTION

The European electric power systems integrates every day larger shares of renewable energy sources, making more distributed energy resources active in the distribution networks. These new variable resources require finding complementary resources, flexible enough to keep the system in balance. Traditionally, this flexibility has been provided by centralized flexible power plants. However, flexibility can also be provided by the demand-side, even from small resources. By altering the consumption patterns of multiple residential devices, a pool of residential consumers can contribute to system stability, for example by providing balancing reserves to the system operator, through an aggregator as an intermediary.

The FLEXCoop project, funded via the Horizon 2020 programme grant agreement no. 773909, has developed a complete automated demand response tool suite, directed towards the activation of flexibility of residential electricity customers, enabling flexibility

to fulfil different services to the grid, and opening the possibility for energy cooperatives and other energy communities to take the role of flexibility aggregators. FLEXCoop focuses on energy cooperatives and their role in democratizing the energy market.

The HOLISDER project, funded through Horizon 2020 programme grant agreement no. 768614, is an innovation action project that couples several mature technologies and integrates them in an open and interoperable framework to activate the whole demand response value chain. It ensures consumer empowerment and transformation into active market players, through implicit and hybrid demand response schemes. This project strongly focuses on buildings as providers of flexibility.

This paper points out the key findings related to standardization and interoperability made by Končar who participated in both projects. It points out some key enabling steps for wider proliferation of demand-side flexibility services throughout the European Union.

FIGURE 1: “FROM GENERATION FOLLOWING CONSUMPTIONS TOWARDS DEMAND FOLLOWS GENERATION” BASED ON ELIA'S VISION*

KEY ACTORS & TECHNICAL SETUP TO ENABLE DEMAND-SIDE FLEXIBILITY

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Demand-side flexibility may be used by a network operator for balancing the whole grid or managing network congestions, or by a balancing responsible party or to balance its own portfolio. An aggregator may gather the necessary resources, forecast their available flexibility, and offer it as a single resource based on the requirements of the flexibility user. The aggregator keeps track of flexibility activations for measurement, verification and eventual remuneration. The aggregator may also offer the device owners insights on their consumption, thanks to dedicated applications.

The following illustration (figure2) depicts a secure, standards-based functional reference architecture required to activate the flexibility value chain. The illustration represents key functions: the entities presented with a single block may also be implemented in a decentralized federated manner.

To activate flexibility, the controllable resources need to receive and execute commands. In the early 2000s, the **OpenADR standard** has been envisioned, to standardize, automate and simplify demand response operations. It has been adopted by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) within the IEC 62746 family of standards. This standard defines the general communication of a demand response control message. To control the loads, gateway devices are required to convert OpenADR messages to the direct commands to the controllable resources. A gateway is a translator, converting the OpenADR requests into direct commands that may be directly interpreted by the controllable asset.

The commands and protocols are notably different for the controllable assets within an apartment or a building, as opposed to ones in an industrial plant. This is the difference between home gateway and the telecontrol gateway. Telecontrol gateways interface with the SCADA systems in an industrial plant and "talk" the industrial control protocols. The residential consumers gateways issue commands to the in-house appliances and devices. A secure, encrypted public-private key pair based infrastructure allowing secure communication over the untrusted Internet channels is also required. To scale the demand response system, setting up dedicated and separate communication channels is not feasible.

FIGURE 2: ACTIVATING THE DEMAND-SIDE FLEXIBILITY CHAIN

KEY FINDINGS

THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRAND-AGNOSTIC SERVICES IS COMPLICATED BY THE MULTITUDE OF IN-HOUSE STANDARDS AND “WALLED GARDEN” APPROACH OF SOME OF THE EQUIPMENT MANUFACTURERS.

For the demand response service to be fulfilled, all the links in the communication channel must function. If only one link among the whole chain fails, none of the flexibility services may be provided. In-house devices do not have a prevailing communication standard. The end-user devices should be, at the same time easy to configure, affordable and support all the standards in the target market – and these are conflicting objectives. Telecontrol gateways, on the other hand, require careful configuration and may require expensive upgrades and downtime.

To attract customers with smart, remotely controllable devices, many equipment manufacturers offer data services in a vertically integrated cloud solution. This goes from a broad range of household devices to solar panel inverters. Manufacturers then offer an easy-to-use web and mobile app services to their clients. In that way, the user data and equipment control are then fully captive to the manufacturer's solution.

Clients may favour such applications to an extent as their experience is comfortable: it simply works with no significant configuration. A competitive mobile and web application is an absolute prerequisite for a flexibility provider. **A simple question of mobile application can make or break the flexibility provider's business case.**

Moreover, several manufacturers do not permit any access to their devices aside from their own cloud-based interfaces. No direct access from the gateway to the device is allowed, even if the device supports an open standard. In some cases, even the warranty is void if the user tries to utilize the nominally existent open standard connection to the device.

To ensure interoperability, a certification framework that examines whether the energy market solutions follow the established open standards and are able to interoperate could be a solution. While manufacturers should remain free to create their own walled-garden solutions, **enforcing the device manufacturers to fully respect a common interoperable standard, alongside their proprietary solutions, would be a significant step onwards to allow brand-agnostic flexibility services.**

SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY IS REQUIRED AT ALL LEVELS; HOWEVER, THE LANDSCAPE IS STILL FRAGMENTED.

The OpenADR / IEC 62746 protocol has been designed out of necessity in a very pragmatic fashion in the US in the early 2000s. Its simplicity makes it widely applicable, however it leaves out many implementation details. Indeed, the standard defines how to carry the message payload, but does not interpret payload semantics. However, for the demand response service to function, it is not enough to have an interoperable protocol as a mere data carrier, the data must be correctly interpreted too.

A common semantic scheme and thus the adherence to common data semantic interpretation is then required, beyond the communication protocol. Message payloads have to be interpreted correctly at both ends: just the communication protocols are not enough to ensure both parties understand each other enough to perform a service. The task of a common information model is to ensure that the message

payloads conform to the proper messaging schema, so that the payload semantics are correctly interpreted at both ends. There are attempts to establish common information models and standardized semantics, but none covers the full demand response value chain. For the market mechanisms on flexibility trading, the USEF¹ standard is quite established, and it delivers the market framework to trade and commoditize the energy flexibility, as well as the canonical tools and nomenclature to be used. At other levels in the demand response value chain, the current situation is comparatively unclear, and currently there is no winner semantic model. However, one of the most promising and well-established semantic interoperability standards for smart devices seems to come from the SAREF² ontology family. At this point, for the whole demand response value chain, **full semantic interoperability is still out of reach and remains the direction for further research and development activities.**

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DATA MINIMIZATION AND CLEAR SECURITY STANDARD ARE KEY TO ENSURE DATA SECURITY AND PRIVACY.

Ensuring the security of communication channels while relying on public, possibly insecure networks is key to wide proliferation of demand-side flexibility services. However, security and privacy on the one hand, and ease of configuration on the other, may represent conflicting objectives. For example, easy-to-use standards often open the devices to adverse attacks. A central cloud-based configuration system may simplify the device deployment but becomes problematic with regards to privacy and data minimization. In most cases a middleware solution is the central point attackers would target. In that regard, following **the data minimization principle is key to prevent attacks**. The components requiring sensitive and personally identifiable user data should be reduced to the strictly necessary. All interfaces should be secured, together with involved devices, and the established cryptographic standards should be used instead of proprietary solutions.

Our proposal is to use an established standard for authentication, such as OAuth2.0 and couple it with the OpenADR protocol. Access to the certificate issuer should be restricted to authenticated users, thereby tying the device to the user. The certificate is then used for signing off all communication from that device. The device certificate issuer should preferably be the entity already handling the user private data (for instance, the energy cooperative the user is already a member of). This way the user sensitive data exposure is minimized, no default certificates are included into the firmware of the user premises devices. This way the risk of compromised default certificate is mitigated, and at the same time, invalid or compromised certificates or tokens can be revoked. This lowers the opportunities for system-wide cyber security attacks.

To ensure end-user privacy in the emerging sector of energy data related services, **an obligatory security standard enforcing the minimal security requirements of demand-side flexibility solutions is important.**

Technical requirements may be complemented with contractual and legal requirements related to the General Data Protection Regulation. The roles of data processors and data controllers should be clearly assigned, and demand-side flexibility services should be accompanied with clear information on data handling responsibilities in a clear and transparent language approved through explicit user consent.

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THE AUTOMATIC CONFIGURATION OF RESIDENTIAL DEVICES WOULD ENABLE BROADER ACCESS TO DEMAND-SIDE FLEXIBILITY SERVICES.

The absence of a common communication standard makes the integration of devices from different manufacturers (ex: a heat pump and water boiler) in a single flexibility offer very difficult. **The availability of a "plug-and-play" configuration for all user's devices would greatly widen the range of possible end-users.**

The generalisation of “plug-and-play” configuration may come to life as a by-product of adopting a common open communication protocol and having a winner semantic standard. The household gateways would then need to support a reduced set of protocols, and converters for popular legacy devices may appear in the market. To the contrary, as of today, not being able to easily infer and configure the local devices carries significant business risks for an aggregator. Until the common standard emerges, the only viable solution remains a deep dive into a particular market segment and fine-tuning the gateway to currently the most popular equipment, including heuristic methods to recognize the default device configurations. This requires trial and error and providing support to the users.

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UNEVEN DEMAND RESPONSE MARKET DEVELOPMENT ACROSS EUROPE AND UNCOMPLETED FRAMEWORKS FOR AGGREGATION STILL HAMPER THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEMAND-SIDE SERVICES.

The new Electricity Directive (EU 2019/941-944) issued in 2019 is a critical milestone to enable demand response services throughout Europe. However, there are still very notable barriers to their wide adoption. **The Expert Group 3 of the European Smart Grids Task Force analysed the remaining gaps for aggregator businesses. Its findings³ broadly overlap and complement the experiences of HOLISDER and FLEXCoop in the past three years.**

The Expert Group identified a lack of standardization, the absence of a common framework for demand-side service providers, the absence of a framework for the integration of implicit and explicit demand response, together with issues related to data access and data sharing. EU member states still have very different positions towards the concept of demand response markets (DR), as confirmed by the pilot experiences from Finland, Great Britain, Greece, The Netherlands, Serbia and Spain. Finally, other difficulties are related to the uneven deployment of smart metering devices among EU countries and the different capabilities of these devices and the utilities to support the consumer data services.

CONCLUSION During the past years, tremendous improvements took place in terms of standardization and interoperability in smart grids. From few scattered services in a handful of EU countries, a whole regulatory framework is being put in place within the Clean Energy Package, operational and commercial standards have emerged with initiatives like USEF and a diffuse set of communication protocols and semantics have emerged supporting the implementation of a first generation of technologies and services at residential level. However, a lot remains to be performed to unlock the potential of demand-side flexibility. We hope the above observations and recommendations may contribute to the EU debate and support market actors and decision-makers in fine-tuning the market rules, which will allow to tap the massive potential of demand-side flexibility.

¹ Universal Smart Energy Framework, more info at: <https://www.usef.energy/>

² Smart Applications REFerence Ontology, more info at: <https://saref.etsi.org/>

³ European Smart Grids Task Force Expert Group 3 – Final Report: Demand Side Flexibility: Perceived Barriers and Proposed Recommendations, https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/eg3_final_report_demand_side_flexibility_2019.04.15.pdf